

Results of the ZKI Top Trends survey conducted by the ZKI Strategy and Organization working group for 2024

Malte Dreyer, Humboldt University of Berlin, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1775-8622>

malte.dreyer@hu-berlin.de

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Introduction

The Strategy and Organization working group of the ZKI Association¹ conducts an annual survey on the most important topics and trends of IT institutions from universities and research institutes. The survey results are intended to help keep an eye on important developments, topics and best practices and to keep pace with the extensive topics of digitalization and the rapid renewal of technologies.

The core survey addresses the most important topics and changes in a standardized form. In addition, individual focal points that concern many institutions are surveyed each year. For 2024, the focus questions were in the area of **digital sovereignty**:

- Questions on the dimensions of digital sovereignty and the role of open source software, cloud services and partnerships.
- Issues relating to IT security and cyber attacks.

The survey also asks about IT governance models and the CDO and CISO positions.

The survey is completed by CIOs, data center managers, IT directors and people in similar roles. Answering all questions is optional. The results of the Top Trends Survey 2024 are presented in this article .

In 2024, 180 universities from Germany, Austria and Switzerland took part in the survey. Most respondents answered the survey in less than 9 minutes, 75% in less than 20 minutes.

The survey results from the previous year 2023 are available at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7599852>

¹ <https://www.zki.de/>

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Summary

With 180 participants, this year's survey got more response than in previous years. This is partly due to the participation of universities from Austria and Switzerland, but also to a higher level of participation from German universities.

Cybersecurity and IT security are mentioned in almost all questions, both in the context of security technologies and in relation to data protection and compliance. This year, the answers focus on the challenges of setting up emergency management and the use of additional components in this context. Over 80% of universities have already established the position of a CISO². The role of a CDO is currently only established at around 18% of universities. The majority of the participating universities follow the guidelines of the BSI baseline protection in the development of the ISMS. It is a great success for the ZKI Information Security Working Group that around half of the BSI mentions are attributable to the specific recommendations for universities - the BSI-ZKI IT baseline protection profile for universities. At around 14%, the number of mentions relating to the use of the ISO27K series is lower. Almost half of the participating universities have already involved a service provider for responding to cyber incidents. On a scale of 1 - very low - to 10 - very high - the threat level for cyberattacks on their own institution is rated as high at around 8 on average. In Austria, this value is even slightly higher. The challenges of finding and retaining qualified IT specialists account for an even greater proportion of the responses than in previous years. This is also reflected in the responses regarding the redesign of the IT organization, dealing with modern forms of work and new organizational structures. The topic of digital transformation pervades the answers to most questions. This generally includes the switch to digital processes, but also very specific answers on the conversion of administrative processes. The use of internal or external clouds and cloud technologies, as well as a wide range of collaborations, show great dynamism in the efforts of IT centers to meet the need for new services and technologies. This year, "automation" is an answer that is mentioned very frequently for the first time in connection with "digitalization". At the same time, automation is also mentioned in the context of new technologies and AI as an enabling technology foundation for digitalization. The significantly increased mention of container technologies should also be seen in this context.

Compared to previous years, the topics of governance and compliance are mentioned far more frequently in the responses. This is particularly evident in the question "Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant in the coming year?". Compared to previous years, there are very extensive answers on standards and laws that are being sought for the company and a far greater mention of policies as the basis for structured consideration processes and decisions. As a stronger ability to make statements regarding compliance also goes hand in hand with clearer and more explicit governance for the management of IT centers, answers regarding the redesign of IT centers, restructuring, quality assurance measures and project management methods are also increasing.

² Chief Information Security Officer - often also referred to as "IT Security Officer"

The relevant top trends for the ZKI community in 2024 are the following topics:

Category	Quantity
IT and cyber security	41
Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)	34
Staff shortage and shortage of skilled workers	24
Digitization and automation	21
Cloud technologies and infrastructure	15
Cooperation and networking	12
Financing and profitability	12
Cybercrime and threat management	12
Legal aspects and compliance management	11
New technologies and innovations	10
Digital sovereignty and independence	10
Sustainability and green IT	9
Education and research in the digital age	9
Modern forms of work and organizational models	7
Long-term archiving and data management	6

The survey asks on the one hand about general IT trends and on the other hand about trends that are particularly relevant for the own institution (see core survey). The trends with the highest relevance for the institutions are shown here. In the past, there was a greater difference between the general and relevant topics, but this difference has become increasingly smaller in recent years. This year, the responses differ only in a more specific description of the relevant topics and are largely identical in terms of the topics. In the previous year, the topic of "AI" was mentioned very frequently in the general trends, but was not yet seen as relevant for the respondents' own institution. This has changed for 2024 and the topic has reached second place in terms of mentions.

Key issues 2024 - Digital sovereignty

The topic of "digital sovereignty" (DS) is becoming increasingly important for universities and research institutions due to the concentration of service provider structures, rising license costs, data protection and IT security considerations, changing and unpredictable framework conditions and sustainability aspects. The topic revolves around the question of the extent to which institutions can decide on the use of digital resources, data and infrastructures themselves or must accept changes from the market. For universities, digital sovereignty more specifically means the extent to which they can retain self-determination over their digital technologies, systems and data and thus maintain their freedom of teaching and research.

The German Science and Humanities Council has also taken a position on the topic with its publication "Recommendations on the sovereignty and security of science in the digital space"³. In its recommendations, the Council assigns particular importance to the science system with regard to the promotion of digital sovereignty and recommends using existing competencies and cooperation structures in a targeted manner to increase digital sovereignty.

IT centers are required to interpret the topic of digital sovereignty for themselves and to derive concrete measures and develop strategies to promote a sustainable positioning of their service portfolio. The topic was discussed in the ZKI working group in 2023 and various dimensions were identified as to how the issues surrounding digital sovereignty influence the strategy and actions of IT centers⁴. This gave rise to the idea of selecting "Digital Sovereignty" as the focus topic for the upcoming Top Trends survey in order to gain a broader overview of how Digital Sovereignty is already being promoted at universities and which fields of action the topic is associated with.

The main questions on the topic of digital sovereignty in the survey were:

- In your opinion, what are the most important dimensions or areas of responsibility that make up the "digital sovereignty" of your university?
- What role do open-source technologies play in your efforts to achieve digital sovereignty?
- What role do cloud services and infrastructures outside your organization play in implementing your digital sovereignty strategy, and how do you secure them?
- What partnerships and collaborations does your institution maintain with other universities or research institutions to strengthen digital sovereignty?
- What measures has your organization taken to ensure the security and integrity of its IT infrastructure?
- According to which standard is the information security management system ISMS developed at your institution?
- Have you integrated a service provider for incident response?
- How do you assess the risk of cyberattacks on your facility?

Summary of the answers

The answers show how complex the topic of digital sovereignty is and they illustrate that extensive activities already exist at universities. Particularly noteworthy here are the far-reaching collaborations at all levels, not only at the level of service provision, but also in the cooperation for the development of topics, for support services and for platforms for direct exchange. In addition to

³ German Council of Science and Humanities (2023): Recommendations on the sovereignty and security of science in the digital space; Cologne. <https://doi.org/10.57674/m6pk-dt95>

⁴ Examples of aspects of DS that are often not directly assigned to the topic are rental licenses for access points or storage solutions as well as questions about standardized interfaces in the area of media technology.

answers on specific operating models, such as on-premises, university clouds, external clouds or SaaS, the location of operations within Germany or Europe is listed as a core criterion in connection with data protection challenges. A focus on contract design with external service providers, exit strategies, multi-vendor approaches and the need for open interfaces are also frequently mentioned.

The results show that there is a very differentiated and reflective attitude towards the use of cloud services. This complex of issues goes hand in hand with clearer control of the decision-making process for the use of software and the procurement of licenses in line with policies. A close connection with the accessibility and introduction of innovative technologies is also frequently mentioned, which would otherwise not be feasible for many universities due to the shortage of staff and specialists. There is a clear desideratum here for additional collaborative approaches in order to make such innovative topics available to more universities, at least in cooperation between universities, within the framework of alliances or in working groups.

In addition to the operating and contracting forms, there are many mentions aimed at establishing alternatives for existing products. Open-source policies are a frequently described approach for resolving vendor lock-ins or avoiding them in the future. The vast majority of responses give open-source software (OSS) a major role or have established an open source first policy. In addition to technological independence, the greater flexibility and adaptability of open-source approaches are also emphasized. In contrast, acceptance problems are also mentioned when using OSS.

Last but not least, the demand for data sovereignty also relates to the data security of their own infrastructure, meaning that IT security issues are a necessary prerequisite for the digital sovereignty of the institutions. In this context, most responses describe increased activities for the development of an ISMS (Information Security Management System) and BCM (Business Continuity Management) or the development of in-house personnel capacities and the involvement of external services for these purposes. These change processes are accompanied by extensive technical measures, e.g., in the areas of identity and access management, network security and securing the basic infrastructure for virtualization.

In this area, cost considerations are also increasingly mentioned as a motivation for committing to the topic of digital sovereignty in light of the lack of budget increases or even budget cuts. Conversely, this means that many universities also expect concrete cost benefits from a stronger commitment to digital sovereignty.

In your opinion, what are the most important dimensions or areas of responsibility that make up the "digital sovereignty" of your university?

The question received 233 responses from 97 universities. The answers are distributed as follows.

Category	Number of mentions
On-premises operation	34
Open source software	31
Establishment of alternatives	18
Exit contracts for cloud providers	11
Technological independence	10
Data sovereignty and data protection	9
Implementation of standards	9
Collaboration/cooperation	8
Operating models and data control	7
Cloud strategy	6
Software strategy	5
In-house development and innovation	5
Challenges during implementation	5
Digital skills and resources	4

The following partially overlapping or even contradictory dimensions were identified in the responses to the thematic areas of digital sovereignty.

Operating models and data control: This category deals with the avoidance of vendor lock-ins, on-premise operation, EU/DE contract data processing, sovereignty over data and data protection, the introduction of standards for the sovereignty of individual providers, exit strategies and contracts for cloud providers.

Software strategy: The focus here is on the use of open-source software, the establishment of alternative approaches, the multi-vendor approach and the strengthening of open-source communities.

Technological independence: This is about not being too dependent on external providers, avoiding a vendor lock-in and implementing standards for technological independence.

Cloud strategy: This category includes strategic considerations between cloud and local operation, open interfaces for connected systems, cross-university private clouds and exit strategies for cloud providers.

Digital skills and resources: The aim is to promote the strengthening of digital skills among students and employees, to consider alternative approaches to independence and expertise, to apply standardization measures and to provide internal training.

Implementation challenges: The challenges of implementing on-premises operation and the challenges of switching due to staff shortages or a lack of operational alternatives are highlighted.

Collaboration/Cooperation: This category deals with cooperation with other universities, the creation of cooperation ecosystems and the involvement of other organizations in software selection and negotiations with providers.

Data security and data protection: The topics addressed are security awareness among IT managers, the lack of resources for security and the focus on data protection.

In-house development and innovation: This relates to the development of in-house development skills, detailed considerations regarding software usage and the consideration of in-house developments.

What role do open-source technologies play in your efforts to achieve digital sovereignty?

There were 116 responses to this question from 98 universities, which can be broken down into the following categories.

Category	Quantity
Limited or subordinate role	16
Weighing up the advantages and disadvantages	15
Open-Source First	14
Flexibility and adaptability	14
Cost management and budget restrictions	12
Independence and avoidance of vendor lock-in	8
Professionalization and support	8
High priority and active use	6
Lack of use or acceptance	4
Security and compliance considerations	4
Specific areas of application	3
Complementary use to commercial software	3

The answers can be divided into the following categories.

Limited or subordinate role: Responses that indicate that open-source technologies play a limited or subordinate role. Resource limitations or a lack of expertise are frequently cited as reasons for this.

Weighing up advantages and disadvantages: Answers that demonstrate a nuanced view by weighing up the advantages and disadvantages of open source versus proprietary software for each individual use.

Open-Source First: Responses that indicate a strategic decision to integrate open-source technologies, often as part of an open source first strategy.

Flexibility and customizability: Answers that emphasize the flexibility and customizability of open-source software to meet specific needs.

Cost management and budget constraints: Answers that emphasize the use of open source as a cost-effective solution, especially with budget constraints.

Independence and avoidance of vendor lock-in: Answers that point to the importance of open source for independence from individual software providers and the avoidance of vendor lock-ins.

Professionalization and support: Answers that emphasize the importance of professional support for open-source technologies.

High priority and active use: Responses that emphasize that open-source technologies play a central role and are actively used.

Lack of use or acceptance: Responses indicating that open-source technologies are not used or are met with resistance, often due to a lack of staff or skills.

Security and compliance considerations: Answers that address security considerations and compliance requirements related to open-source technologies.

Specific areas of application: Answers that point to specific areas where open-source technologies are preferred, such as web services or learning management systems.

Complementary use to commercial software: Answers that describe the use of open source as a complement to commercial software.

The answers to this question show a particularly high degree of heterogeneity. For this reason, we also investigated how the answers differ between large and small universities.

Rather large universities emphasize a major role of open source, open source-first strategies, server operation on Linux, the historical importance of OSS for universities and increased support costs for OSS. Rather smaller universities emphasize the cost aspects of using OSS, the requirement that OSS must also be security-tested, a consideration of functionalities in relation to maintenance costs and a focus on research and teaching.

Specific projects and products were also named in this question:

- BigBlueButton
- Bitwarden
- BookStack
- Docker
- Linux
- Nextcloud
- OpenProject
- OpenStack
- Suricata
- Znuun/OTRS

What role do cloud services and infrastructures outside your organization play in implementing your digital sovereignty strategy, and how do you secure them?

There were 106 responses to this question from 88 universities with the following distribution.

Category	Quantity
Security & data protection challenges	13
Large roll	12
Irrelevant	8
Small roll	8
Increasingly important	7
Within the scope of cooperations	7
Contract management challenges	7
Enabling technology access	6
As part of a multi-cloud strategy	5
Solution approach for personnel & specialist shortage	5
Lack of awareness of the problem	4
Training & awareness	3
Enabling better service levels	2
Only with existing provider flexibility	2

The answers to this question can be categorized as follows.

Security & data protection challenges: There are major challenges in coordinating the necessary security and data protection measures for the use of cloud services.

Major role: Cloud services are a central component of the digital infrastructure and strategy.

Irrelevant: Cloud services have no influence on the institution's digital strategy.

Small role: Cloud services are only used to a limited extent or for specific purposes.

Increasingly important: the importance of cloud services is growing.

Within the framework of cooperations: Use of cloud services as part of partnerships with other universities.

Challenges in contract management: Difficulties and complexity in the management of cloud contracts.

Enabling technology access: Cloud services provide access to advanced technologies.

Multi-cloud strategy: Pursuing an approach that involves several cloud providers.

Staff and specialist shortages: Cloud services as a solution to staff and specialist shortages.

Lack of awareness of the problem: Low awareness of problems and risks associated with cloud services.

Training & awareness: Need for training and awareness in the use of cloud services.

Service levels: Cloud services enable improved service quality.

Provider flexibility: Preference for cloud services where it is easy to switch providers.

Due to the great heterogeneity of the responses, it was also examined how the responses differed between larger and smaller universities. Rather large universities emphasize the use of community cloud solutions in the area of collaboration, the use of AWS, Azure and Google, the use of DFN services and services from other universities. Smaller universities tend to emphasize the aspects of scalability and availability, the need for sensitization and awareness, data protection issues and the challenges associated with contract, cost and support management for cloud services. It is frequently emphasized that only a few contracts are concluded for cloud services, but that these are highly relevant for the university.

The following products or organizations were mentioned in the context of this question.

- BBB (BigBlueButton)
- COSINEX procurement portal
- DFN (German Research Network)
- FAUbox (Bavarian PowerFolder instance)
- iCAS
- Jitsi
- M365 (Microsoft 365)/ Microsoft Office
- MATLAB
- Microsoft Azure
- Microsoft Exchange
- Microsoft Sharepoint
- Microsoft Teams
- Overleaf
- SAP
- SWITCHcloud
- VEEAM
- Zoom/Zoom X

What partnerships and collaborations does your institution maintain with other universities or research institutions to strengthen digital sovereignty?

This question was answered by 89 universities with 111 responses. The answers can be categorized as follows.

Category	Quantity
Regional and nationwide cooperation	16
Participation in specialized alliances and projects	13
Cooperation in special areas	11
Membership in IT networks and associations	10
Specific university partnerships	10
Regular exchange and coordination	10
Cooperative software and infrastructure projects	10
No partnerships or cooperations	9
Informal exchange of experience and personal contacts	9
Formation and use of cooperatives and associations	7
Use of shared resources	6
International and national trade associations and initiatives	6
Initiatives for digital research infrastructure	6
Exchange of cloud and IT services	5
Cooperation in the field of high-performance computing	4
Cooperation for emergency and crisis situations	4

The answers to this question can be grouped into the following categories.

Regional and nationwide cooperations: This category covers partnerships that focus on a specific geographic region.

Participation in specialized alliances and projects: This category includes participation in specialized projects and alliances with a focused objective.

Cooperation in special areas: Examples include "Cooperation in the area of Current Research Information System (CRIS)", "Cooperation in the area of IT security". This category includes collaborations that focus on specific areas or topics.

Memberships in IT networks and associations: Includes answers such as ZKI membership, DFN membership, OSBA membership. This category includes participation in networks and associations specializing in IT and digital infrastructure.

Specific university partnerships: Here, specific university names are mentioned that refer to specific bilateral collaborations.

Regular exchange and coordination: This category refers to regular meetings and coordination between different institutions.

Cooperative software and infrastructure projects: This category includes cooperative projects in the area of software and infrastructure.

No partnerships or collaborations: This category includes universities that state that they have no relevant partnerships.

Informal exchange of experience and personal contacts: This category refers to less formal forms of exchange and cooperation.

Formation and use of cooperatives and associations: This category includes the formation of cooperatives or alliances to strengthen digital sovereignty.

Use of shared resources: Examples include "Use of cross-university services for backup and cloud storage", "Shared data center". This category focuses on the shared use of resources and infrastructures.

International and national professional associations and initiatives: Answers such as "Involvement in AcoNet", "Participation in European initiatives such as Gaia-X". Supra-regional and international professional associations and initiatives are mentioned here.

Digital research infrastructure initiatives: This category concerns initiatives that are specifically aimed at improving the digital research infrastructure.

Exchange of cloud and IT services: Answers such as "Use of the DFN cloud", "Community cloud solutions". This category concerns specific services in the IT sector that are used or offered by the universities.

Cooperation in the field of high-performance computing: includes cooperation between universities in the use of high-performance computers and systems. This can include the joint use of computing resources, the development of new technologies and the promotion of research projects in this area.

Cooperation for emergency and crisis situations: refers to cooperation between universities in the preparation and management of emergencies and crises. This can include the development of emergency plans, training of employees and the provision of resources for emergencies.

The following products or organizations were named in the responses.

- ACOmarket (Austrian Academic Computer Network Marketplace)
- AcoNet (Austrian Academic Computer Network)
- Bavarian Digital Network
- BMBWF (Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research)
- CAMPUSonline (Austrian Campus Management System)
- CRIS NRW Research Data Management
- DFN Cloud
- DFN membership (German Research Network)
- DH-NRW (Digital Humanities North Rhine-Westphalia)
- ELAN (Elearning Academic Network Lower Saxony)
- European University Alliances
- Gaia-X (data infrastructure for Europe)
- GIT (Society for Computer Science in Thuringia)
- GWDG (Göttingen Society for Scientific Data Processing)
- HDN (Digital University of Lower Saxony)
- HIS cooperative member (University Information Systems)
- LANIT (state-wide networks for IT in Lower Saxony)
- LRZ (Leibniz Supercomputing Center)
- NFDI (National Research Data Infrastructure)
- NHR (National High Performance Computing)
- NREN (National Research and Education Network) (SWITCH)

- NRW partnerships (partnerships in North Rhine-Westphalia)
- OSBA membership (Open Source Business Alliance)
- Rhineland-Palatinate Data Center Alliance
- Uniko (Austrian University Conference)
- ZKI membership (Centers for Communication and Information Processing)

What measures has your organization taken to ensure the security and integrity of its IT infrastructure?

The question was answered by 86 universities with 133 responses.

Category	Quantity
IT management and governance	14
Personnel and resources	14
Firewall and network security	11
Emergency planning and response capability	8
Awareness and training	7
External services and partnerships	7
Security measures and audits	6
Authentication and access control	5
Compliance and standards	4
Virtualization and infrastructure management	2

The following categories were formed from the responses.

IT management and governance: The establishment of an ISMS (Information Security Management System) and BCM (Business Continuity Management) is necessary for a structured approach to IT security management. Compliance with governance measures contributes to the overall stability and resilience of IT systems.

Personnel and resources: The development of specialized capacities for IT security and the promotion of IT security skills at all levels are essential in order to meet the growing security challenges.

Firewall and network security: The implementation of next-generation firewalls and advanced antivirus solutions, together with technologies such as geoblocking and the use of a web application firewall (WAF), strengthen the defense against network attacks.

Contingency planning and response: Developing contingency plans and preparing for incident response is critical to responding quickly and efficiently to security incidents.

Awareness and training: Awareness and training are important to strengthen the human element of cyber security. Phishing simulations and regular training can increase awareness of cyber threats and help to reduce security incidents.

External services and partnerships: Working with external security experts and service providers, such as a SOC (Security Operations Center), can significantly improve the ability to detect and respond to security incidents.

Security measures and audits: Regular security audits, penetration tests and vulnerability scans are essential elements for identifying and eliminating security gaps.

Authentication and access control: MFA (multi-factor authentication) and 2FA (two-factor authentication) are effective methods to prevent unauthorized access. Enforcing strong password rules and raising awareness of external emails also increases security.

Compliance and standards: Compliance with standards such as ISO 27001 and BSI as well as compliance with GDPR requirements are not only legally required, but also a sign of best practice in the area of security.

Virtualization and infrastructure management: Switching from VMWare to OpenStack/Proxmox/Ceph could offer cost advantages and allow more flexibility in the management of the virtual infrastructure. The challenge lies in migration and dealing with potential compatibility issues. Hardening the virtual infrastructure and the redundant structure of all central IT resources are crucial for operational security.

The following products and organizations were named in the responses.

- **DFN-Cert:** A security service provider for research and educational institutions.
- **eduroam:** A secure WLAN access service for educational institutions.
- **eduVPN:** A Virtual Private Network (VPN) for educational institutions.
- **GrayLog Enterprise Security:** A log file analysis platform.
- **Greenbone:** A vulnerability scanner that is used to identify security gaps and strengthen IT security.
- **ISO 27001 and NIST:** These are security standards that are mentioned to emphasize compliance with best practices.
- **Multi-factor authentication (MFA) and two-factor authentication (2FA):** These are referred to as methods for access control and increased security.
- **Next-generation firewalls:** These are mentioned as part of network security.
- **Palo Alto Next-Generation Firewalls:** A specific brand of next-generation firewalls.
- **Proofpoint ET Pro Rule Set:** A rule set for security.
- **Proxmox/Ceph:** A switch to Proxmox and Ceph is being discussed as a possible alternative to VMWare.
- **Semperi's Purple Knight:** A solution for securing Active Directory.
- **Sentinel One:** An endpoint security product is mentioned.
- **Sophos:** One company that offers security solutions is mentioned in relation to client protection.
- **Suricata:** An intrusion detection system (IDS).
- **VMWare:** This product is mentioned in connection with virtualization and infrastructure management.
- **WebApplicationFirewall (WAF):** A special firewall for web applications to strengthen security against web attacks.

According to which standard is the information security management system ISMS developed at your institution?

The following distribution of answers was obtained for this question.

The following table shows a breakdown by the size of the university.

The following chart shows a breakdown by type of university.

Have you integrated a service provider for incident response?

Other names for similar services include "APT service provider", "response retainer" or "cyber incident response retainer".

55 universities have already integrated a service provider, 47 have not yet done so. The following diagram illustrates this distribution.

Provider IR total; n=102

The distribution among the participating countries for this survey is shown in the following charts.

How do you rate the risk of cyber attacks on your institution?

The participants' rating of their own university's vulnerability to cyber attacks are presented below.

The average value across all countries is 7.9.

The following chart shows the assessments from Germany. The average value is 7.8.

The following chart shows the assessment of the risk of cyberattacks by the participants from Austria. The average value is 8.4.

In the participating universities from Switzerland, the average risk of cyberattacks is given as 8.0.

Changes in the top trends compared to the previous year

These questions are intended to shed light on how the top trends relevant to IT institutions at universities and research institutes have changed over the years.

Compared to the previous year, the significance of the top trends has changed as follows:

The top topics of increasing importance are:

The top topics with the greatest decreasing importance are:

The following chart, based on the data from 2023, clearly shows how the topics have changed in the rankings within the top trends between 2021 and 2024.

For the year 2024, there are some ambiguities, as, for example, the categories "staff shortage" and "shortage of skilled workers" were sometimes named separately and, for example, digitalization was not yet so strongly divided into the sub-areas "digitalization in general" and "digitalization of administration".

Trend	Place in the relevant top trends			
	2024	2023	2022	2021
IT security	1	1	1	2
Cloud	5	2	2	1
Digital transformation	4	3	5	3
Staff shortage	3	4	3	9
Digital sovereignty		5	9	
Skills shortage	3	6		
Digitization of administration	4	7	3	
Cooperations	6	8		8
OZG		9		
Automation	4	10		

IT governance

In addition to the question about the IT governance model, since 2022 the survey has also asked whether the position of Chief Digital Officer (CDO) has been established at the institution.

Which organizational model for IT governance is used at your university or research institution?

The distribution for the participating facilities in 2024 is shown below.

The table shows the number of mentions.

IT governance model	Number of mentions
Head of a central IT facility as CIO	47
CIO with staff function in the presidential staff	33
CIO committee	31
CIO model is not established	30
Chancellor or Vice President / as CIO	21
Miscellaneous	6

The following diagrams show the distribution of the IT governance model according to the size of the universities.

Does your institution have a Chief Digital Officer (CDO) position?

Since 2022, respondents were also asked whether the position of Chief Digital Officer (CDO) had been established at their own institution. Outside of this survey, CDOs are often reported to be responsible for supporting digital transformation, developing a digital strategy, digitalizing processes, coordinating different areas of the universities and promoting digital skills.

In the previous year 2023, 14% of participants stated that this position had already been established at their institution.

Overall, the role is not pronounced at over 80% of the participating universities.

CDO total; n=157

CDO	Number of mentions
No	129
Yes	28

The following diagram shows the distribution across the countries of the participating universities.

The figures for the individual countries are as follows.

The following charts show the status of the establishment of CDOs by size of the organization.

Does your institution have a Chief Information Security Officer (CISO) position?

Chief Information Security Officers or IT security officers are generally responsible for the development and operation of the information security management system at universities. They manage risk, establish and review IT security standards, carry out training and awareness measures, support crisis management and coordinate the cooperation between the various IT security institutions at a university. They therefore play a key role in the IT security of universities.

Against this backdrop, the question of establishing a corresponding position was included this year. A corresponding position has already been created at over 80% of the participating institutions. A country comparison shows a slightly lower proportion for Austria and Switzerland. However, the proportion increases with the size of an institution. Institutions with more than 15,000 students have almost universally already established comparable positions in all countries.

This question was answered by 175 participants.

CISO total; n=175

CISO	Number of mentions
Yes	141
No	34

The following illustrations provide a comparison of the participating countries.

The following charts show the responses to the establishment of a CISO role in relation to the size of the university.

Results of the core survey

Each year, twelve identical questions are asked in the survey, which are answered as free text. The response texts were normalized and categories were derived from the answers. In some cases, parts of particularly frequently mentioned aspects were integrated into the description of the category. The number of mentions for the categories was then counted.

What top trends do you see in the IT sector in general?

92 participants gave up to 5 answers to this question. The following frequencies were assigned to the categories.

Category	Quantity
Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)	61
Cloud technologies and infrastructure	56
IT security	51
Cybersecurity	38
Digitization and automation	22
Staff shortage and shortage of skilled workers	21
Digital sovereignty and independence	19
Cooperation and networking	7
Sustainability and green IT	5
Personnel management	2

The general top trends with at least two mentions can be divided into the following categories.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML): This category includes all mentions related to AI/ML, including the use of AI tools, the integration of AI in various areas such as teaching, administration and support, and the use of AI for decision support.

Cloud technologies and infrastructure: This category includes all mentions relating to cloud technologies, including the use of cloud services, the migration of software and systems to the cloud, the optimization of cloud solutions and cooperation with large cloud providers.

IT security: This category includes all mentions relating to IT security, including implementing security measures, improving IT security, ensuring compliance and promoting security awareness.

Cybersecurity: This category includes all mentions relating to cybersecurity, including protection against cyberattacks and preparation for security incidents.

Digitalization and automation: This category includes all mentions related to automation, including the use of AI-based automation tools and the implementation of automated processes.

Staff shortage and skills shortage: This category includes all mentions relating to the skills shortage in the IT sector, including the shortage of qualified IT security specialists and the challenges of recruiting specialists.

Digital sovereignty and independence: This category includes all mentions related to digital sovereignty, including ensuring data sovereignty, complying with legal requirements and implementing security measures to ensure digital sovereignty.

Cooperation and networking: This category includes all mentions relating to cooperation with other universities.

Sustainability and Green IT: This category includes all mentions relating to sustainable IT measures, including the more efficient operation of data centers, the use of energy-efficient technologies and the promotion of sustainability aspects.

Personnel management: This category includes all mentions relating to personnel management, including the challenges of salary and the introduction of flexible and modern working methods.

Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?

92 universities gave up to 5 answers to this question. The following results are distributed across the categories. The responses are largely identical between the countries and there are only minor differences in the rankings. Only the area of cloud services and cloud technologies is mentioned to a lesser extent in Austria.

Category	Quantity
IT and cyber security	41
Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)	34
Staff shortage and shortage of skilled workers	24
Digitization and automation	21
Cloud technologies and infrastructure	15
Cooperation and networking	12
Financing and profitability	12
Cybercrime and threat management	12
Legal aspects and compliance management	11
New technologies and innovations	10
Digital sovereignty and independence	10
Sustainability and green IT	9
Education and research in the digital age	9
Modern forms of work and organizational models	7
Long-term archiving and data management	6

The following frequencies result for Austria with 15 participating universities in this question.

Category	Quantity
IT and cyber security	9
Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)	5
Staff shortage and shortage of skilled workers	3
Cybercrime and threat management	3
Digitization and automation	2
Legal aspects and compliance management	2
Digital sovereignty and independence	2

The following results were obtained for Switzerland with 11 participating universities.

Category	Quantity
Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)	8
IT and cyber security	7
Cloud technologies and infrastructure	4
Staff shortage and shortage of skilled workers	4
Digitization and automation	2
Cybercrime and threat management	2
Modern forms of work and organizational models	2

The relevant top trends for 2024 can be broken down into the following categories.

IT and cyber security: This category covers topics relating to the security of information technologies, protection against cyber-attacks and general data security measures.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML): This category deals with the development and application of algorithms that include machine learning and artificial intelligence.

Staff shortage and skills shortage: Addresses the shortage of qualified specialists, particularly in the IT sector, and the challenges of recruiting staff.

Digitalization and automation: Focused on the transition from manual to digital processes, the use of digital technologies to increase efficiency and the automation of administrative processes.

Cloud technologies and infrastructure: Refers to the use and management of cloud-based services, storage solutions and infrastructures.

Cooperation and networking: Concerns cooperation between different institutions, networking within the education sectors and the joint use of resources.

Financing and profitability: Includes financial challenges such as budget constraints and rising costs associated with digitalization and IT infrastructure.

Cybercrime and threat management: Refers to the growing challenges posed by cybercrime and the development of threat management strategies.

Legal aspects and compliance management: Includes topics relating to legal requirements, data protection regulations and compliance with industry standards in the IT sector.

New technologies and innovations: Focused on the introduction of new technologies and innovative solutions in the university environment.

Digital sovereignty and independence: Refers to the ability to make independent and self-determined decisions in the digital space.

Sustainability and Green IT: Focuses on the environmentally friendly design of IT systems and reducing the ecological footprint of technologies.

Education and research in the digital age: Focuses on the transformation of the education and research sector through digital technologies, including new teaching and learning methods.

Modern forms of work and organizational models: Focuses on adapting working methods and organizational structures to modern, digital requirements.

Long-term archiving and data management: Includes strategies for long-term data backup, managing large volumes of data and ensuring data integrity.

Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant in the coming year?
68 universities indicated up to 5 relevant legislative regulations that are particularly relevant for IT centers in 2024.

The answers can be broken down into the following categories.

Data protection and data protection regulations: GDPR, data protection laws, EU-US Data Privacy Framework, Swiss Data Protection Act.

Cybersecurity and information security: NIS2, Cyber Resilience Act, NRW university agreement on cybersecurity, ISMS, KRITIS

Digital transformation and e-government: OZG (Online Access Act), EGov, digital official signature, eIDAS. SDG

Environmental and energy legislation: EEG (Renewable Energy Sources Act), EnEg (Energy Efficiency Act), Green IT legislation.

Employment law and remote work: Employment law regulations for remote work, Accessibility Strengthening Act.

Higher education and education regulation: NRW Higher Education Digital Ordinance, decisions on university funding.

AI regulation: AI Act, dealing with AI at work.

Compliance and standards: ISO 9001, Cloud Act.

International trade and data protection agreements: EU/US data protection agreements, supply chain laws, sanctions lists.

Public procurement: Public procurement law, public procurement, stricter public procurement regulations.

Tax law: Value added tax law, value added tax liability

Accessibility and inclusion: Accessibility

The detailed mentions are:

- Adequacy decision (Data Privacy Framework)
- Labor law regulations for remote work
- Artificial Intelligence Act - AI Act
- Accessibility
- Accessibility Reinforcement Act for websites from 2025
- BÜPF
- Cloud Act
- Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)
- Data protection and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- EU/USA data protection agreement
- Digital Services Act (DSA)
- Digital (official) signatures
- Efficient and ecological server room operation
- E-Government Act (eGovG)
- Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS)
- Energy Efficiency Act (EnEfG)
- Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG)
- Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG 2023)
- Geodata Access Act (GeoZG)
- ID Austria
- ISO 9001
- Critical infrastructures - KRITIS
- Supply Chain Act
- Successor to the Safe Harbor Agreement
- New cantonal data protection law (in 2025)
- Online Access Act (OZG)
- Reformation Public Procurement Act
- Register Modernization Act (Regmog)
- Sanctions lists
- Swiss Data Protection Act (DSG)
- Single Digital Gateway Regulation (SDG Regulation)
- The Network and Information Security (NIS2) Directive - NIS-2 Directive
- Dealing with AI at work
- Value added tax for research institutions (§ 2b UStG)
- Processing system for the monitoring of postal and telecommunications traffic (VVS-ÜPF)
- Ordinance on the Surveillance of Postal and Telecommunications Traffic. (VD-ÜPF)

What topics are you currently working on strategically?

The following table shows the frequency of mentions in relation to these categories from 85 universities.

Category	Quantity
Digitization of the administration	49
Digitization	33
IT organizational restructuring	31
AI use	26
IT and information security	23
Sourcing	12
Resilient IT infrastructures	9
BCM	8
Personnel recruitment	6
Labor law regulations for remote work	5
ECM and DMS	4

The answers can be divided into the following categories.

Digitization of administration: This category includes measures to improve and automate administrative processes through the use of technology.

Digitization: This general category covers the transition from analogue to digital processes and systems in various areas.

IT organizational restructuring: This refers to changes within the IT department to improve its efficiency and performance.

AI use: This category includes the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to optimize processes, support decisions or develop new functions.

IT and information security: This category includes measures to secure IT systems and ensure the confidentiality and integrity of data.

Sourcing: This involves contracting resources and services externally to supplement or expand the company's own IT infrastructure.

Resilient IT infrastructures: This category includes measures to stabilize and make the IT infrastructure resistant to failures or other disruptions.

BCM: Business Continuity Management (BCM) refers to the planning and implementation of measures to restore business processes following disruptions or disasters.

Personnel recruitment: This is about recruiting and retaining qualified personnel for the IT department.

Employment law regulations for remote working: This section deals with legal aspects and precautions for mobile working.

ECM and DMS: Enterprise Content Management (ECM) and document management systems refer to the organization, management and provision of content, such as documents, images and videos.

What new management tasks are you currently working on?

The number of responses for each category from 63 participating universities is shown in the following table.

Category	Quantity
IT management and governance	14
Project management and coordination	11
Strategic orientation and planning	11
Personnel development and recruitment	10
IT security and risk management	10
IT organizational structure and restructuring	8
Digital transformation and innovation	8
IT infrastructure and technology	8
Agility and flexibility	6
Communication and leadership	5
Coordination and cooperation	4
Customer orientation and satisfaction	3

The answers can be divided into the following categories.

IT management and governance: This category deals with the management of IT projects and processes within an organization. It includes topics such as project planning, resource management, quality management and compliance with legal and other requirements.

Project management and coordination: This category deals with the planning, implementation and monitoring of IT projects. It is about how projects can be structured and organized in order to achieve goals and control costs.

Strategic alignment and planning: This category deals with the development and implementation of an IT strategy. It is about how IT measures can be planned and coordinated in order to support the strategic goals.

Personnel development and recruitment: This category deals with the establishment and further development of the IT team and the recruitment of new employees. It is about how to attract, train and motivate talented specialists.

IT security and risk management: This category deals with measures to protect data and systems from threats and risks. It includes topics such as firewalls, encryption, data backup and security audits to identify and eliminate potential vulnerabilities.

IT organizational structure and restructuring: This category deals with the design and redesign of organizational structures in the field of information technology. It is about how IT departments are organized, what roles and responsibilities exist and how these structures can be adapted or changed.

Digital transformation and innovation: This category deals with the use of digital technologies to improve business processes and create new products and services. It is about how digital solutions can be developed and implemented.

IT infrastructure and technology: This category deals with the basic technical infrastructure of universities, including hardware, software and network infrastructure. It is about how these components are selected, installed and maintained.

Agility and flexibility: This category concerns the ability to adapt quickly to changing market requirements and respond flexibly to new challenges. It is about how IT teams can work in an agile way to develop fast and innovative solutions.

Communication and leadership: This category is about effective communication within a team and managing employees. It includes topics such as feedback, conflict resolution and motivation in order to create a positive working atmosphere and lead the team.

Coordination and collaboration: This category is about collaboration and communication between different departments and teams within an organization. The aim is to create efficient processes and ensure that everyone involved is on the same page.

Customer orientation and satisfaction: This category focuses on the users. It is about how IT solutions can be developed and implemented to meet the needs and expectations of users.

In which area are external services becoming more important for you?

78 participating universities gave up to 5 answers to this question. The following numbers were distributed across the categories.

Category	Quantity
IT security	25
Data protection	13
Cloud services	9
Basic services	9
IT consulting	8
IT infrastructure	6
Network security	6
Recruitment	6
Competent contacts in the field of digitalization	5
Emergency planning	5
Teaching and media technology	5
Big Data	4
Market exploration	3
Container orchestration and Kubernetes	3

The answers can be divided into the following categories.

IT security: This category includes external services that deal with the security of IT systems, such as SOC, IR, incident detection and response, forensics, IT consulting and awareness training

Data protection: This category includes external services that help to protect personal data.

Cloud services: This category refers to external services related to cloud computing, such as cloud services, managed services and cloud-based solutions.

Basic services: This category includes external services that cover general IT functions, such as e-mail, printing, etc.

IT consulting: This category includes external services that help with the consulting and planning of IT projects, such as IT consulting and consulting.

IT infrastructure: This category includes external services that help maintain and manage the IT infrastructure of universities, such as network operations and IT infrastructure management.

Network security: This category includes external services that assist in securing and maintaining the security of networks.

Recruitment: This category refers to external services that help with the recruitment and acquisition of IT specialists, such as personnel recruitment and recruiting.

Competent contacts in the field of digitalization: This category includes external services that support digitalization, such as consulting, data analysis or project management.

Emergency planning: This category refers to external services that help in the event of emergencies and IT system failures, such as emergency planning and support.

Teaching and media technology: This category refers to external services in the field of teaching, such as learning management systems, video conferencing functions or e.g. video conferencing systems.

Big Data: This category refers to external services that help manage and analyze large amounts of data.

Market exploration: This category refers to external services that assist in the procurement of IT products and services, such as outsourcing and market exploration for new software products.

Container orchestration: External services to support the orchestration of containers and the deployment and operation of container environments.

In which areas are you investing more than before?

The frequencies of the responses from 80 universities can be assigned to the categories as shown in the following table.

Category	Quantity
IT security	41
Digitization	13
Updating hardware	10
Artificial intelligence (AI)	8
Software licenses	8
Research and scientific computing	7
Network technology	6
Recruitment and development	6
Organizational development	6
Governance and compliance	5
Storage solutions	5
Service contracts	4
Campus Management Systems	3

The answers to this question fall into the following categories.

IT security: This refers to measures to secure IT systems and data. Examples: "IT security", "cybersecurity", "firewall"

Digitalization: This refers to the use of digital technologies to improve processes and services. Examples: "digitalization", "digitalization of processes", "automation".

Updating hardware: This refers to updating outdated hardware such as computers, servers and peripherals.

Artificial intelligence (AI): This refers to the use of algorithms and machine learning methods to analyze and optimize data. Examples: "AI", "AI training/application"

Software licenses: This refers to purchase or rental licenses for software.

Research and scientific computing: This refers to the provision of resources for carrying out calculations and analyses. Examples: "GPU cluster", "computing power", "high performance computing"

Network technology: This refers to the acquisition of network technology.

Recruitment and development: This refers to measures to recruit and develop staff in IT centers.

Organizational development: Measures to improve the internal structures and processes of an organization.

Governance and compliance: guidelines and procedures for monitoring and controlling IT projects and measures.

storage solutions: This refers to the acquisition and updating of storage systems.

Service contracts: This refers to agreements between the universities and external service providers for IT-related services.

Campus Management Systems: The introduction and expansion of campus management systems.

Which technologies are becoming more important for you?

The responses from 68 universities can be summarized in table form as follows.

Category	Quantity
Artificial intelligence (AI)	44
Cloud computing	24
Automation	15
Security technologies and cybersecurity	14
Container technology	9
Big data and data analysis	7
Digital transformation	7
Energy efficiency and green IT	6
Resilience and redundancy	5

The following categories can be formed from the answers.

Artificial intelligence (AI): This category includes technologies based on machine learning, such as AI models as services, AI technologies related to cybersecurity or generative AI.

Cloud computing: This category includes technologies based on the use of cloud-based services, such as SaaS, cloud services, virtual storage systems, private cloud, cloud management and cloud services in teaching and research.

Automation: This category includes technologies that aim to automate processes and workflows, such as automation technologies and AI-based automation.

Security technologies and cybersecurity: This category includes technologies aimed at protecting IT systems from threats, such as security technologies, single sign-on, zero trust, multicloud management and real-time monitoring.

Container technology: This category includes technologies that aim to manage applications in isolated environments, such as containerization, Kubernetes and container solutions.

Big data and data analysis: Technologies that aim to analyze large volumes of data.

Digital transformation: Technologies aimed at digitally transforming organizations and optimizing their processes, such as digital support for workflows in various areas.

Energy efficiency and green IT: Technologies aimed at reducing the energy consumption of IT systems and improving their sustainability.

Resilience and redundancy: This category includes technologies that aim to make IT systems redundant and resilient in order to minimize downtimes and increase performance.

What new services or technologies are you currently introducing?

The responses from 68 universities are distributed as follows in terms of frequency.

Category	Quantity
Artificial intelligence (AI) and ML	17
Cloud technologies	14
Campus management and administration	12
IDM/IAM	11
Document and workflow management	11
Cybersecurity and data protection	9
Data management and storage	9
Microsoft 365 (M365) and MS365	8
Software development and distribution	8
Communication and collaboration	6

The answers can be grouped into the following categories.

Artificial intelligence (AI): This includes everything related to AI and ML technologies, including AI-powered knowledge systems and GenAI.

Cloud technologies: This includes technologies such as OpenStack, cloud telephony, containers/Kubernetes and the total cloud approach with Microsoft Cloud.

Campus management and administration: This refers to university campus management and administration services, including campus management systems, applicant portals and committee management.

Identity and access management (IDM/IAM): This includes services for managing user identities and access rights, such as Active Directory protection, single sign-on (SSO) and multi-factor authentication (MFA).

Document and workflow management: This includes document and workflow process management services, including document management, electronic lab notebook and forms/workflow management and low-code platforms

Cybersecurity and data protection: This includes services and technologies such as ransomware protection, endpoint security, next generation firewall and SIEM/SOC.

Data management and storage: This refers to services for managing data and storage, including data competence centers and storage extensions.

Microsoft 365 (M365): This refers to services and technologies related to the Microsoft 365 Suite.

Software development and distribution: This includes services for software development, distribution and management, including software defined access and software asset management.

Communication and collaboration: This includes services such as Messenger, VoIP, Intranet/Confluence and collaboration tools.

There were some very specific answers to this question, which are listed here.

Electronic laboratory management: Digital platform for recording, storing and managing scientific data and protocols.

Software Defined Access: A concept for defining and managing access to IT resources via software.

Cloud telephony: Telephony systems that work via the Internet and use Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) technology.

Knowledge system with AI support: Information systems that store and analyze large amounts of knowledge in order to make predictions.

Automated server management: Software tools for the automatic control and management of servers.

AI Large Language Models: Advanced AI algorithms for analyzing large amounts of text and extracting information.

Establishment of OpenStack / Private Cloud: Open source code platform for implementing a private cloud infrastructure.

AI-supported learning: Integrating AI into learning experiences to personalize the learning experience.

CEPH Clusterstorage: Software solution for managing large volumes of data in a storage cluster.

What skills would you like to build in your organization over the next year?

The distribution of responses from 62 universities to this question is shown in the following table.

Category	Quantity
IT security	10
Artificial intelligence and machine learning	6
Digital transformation	5
Automation	4
Cloud management	4
Event detection and response	3
Agile project management	3
Crisis management and resilience	3
IT service management	3
Multi-project management	2
Communication and change management	2
Standardization and quality management	2

The following categories can be described from the answers to this question.

IT security: protection against cyber attacks, improvement of IT security or introduction of security measures.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning: Introduction and use of AI technologies and machine learning.

Digital transformation: Development and implementation of new digital technologies and processes to replace manual processes.

Automation: Automation of processes and tasks.

Cloud management: deployment, administration and optimization of cloud-based solutions.

Event detection and response: Early detection and appropriate response to IT events and incidents.

Agile project management: application of agile methods to support projects in the digital transformation environment.

Crisis management and resilience: strengthening the organization's resilience to cyberattacks and other challenges.

IT service management: the set of systems and processes that organizations use to improve the way IT is used

Multi-project management: Effective management of multiple, parallel projects.

Communication and change management: improving communication skills and the ability to implement and manage change.

Standardization and quality management: standardization of processes and standards as well as the introduction and implementation of quality standards.

Particularly noteworthy individual mentions were

MS 365: This refers to the use of Microsoft 365 as productivity software.

AppsAnywhere: AppsAnywhere is a software solution that simplifies the deployment of applications and software in educational institutions.

Azure know-how: Microsoft Azure, a cloud computing platform from Microsoft.

Know-how and operation of cloud solutions: This refers to the knowledge and skills in the operation of cloud solutions, regardless of the specific platform.

Know-how and operation of low-code solutions: Introduction of low-code development platforms to create applications faster.

Centralized MECM management in the Active Directory domain: Centralized management of Microsoft Endpoint Configuration Manager (MECM) in an Active Directory domain.

Open source alternatives in virtualization: Use of open source virtualization solutions instead of proprietary products to reduce costs or increase flexibility.

Which employee skills are becoming more important?

The answers of the 73 participating universities to this question can be presented as follows in relation to the categories.

Category	Quantity
Communication and cooperation skills	16
Project management	11
Awareness of IT security and data protection	13
Flexibility	9
Willingness to learn	7
Adaptability to flexible working methods and forms of organization	6
Openness to everything new	6
Digital competence	6
Data analysis skills	6
Communication skills in processes	5
Awareness (including project success and orchestration of on-premise and cloud services)	4
IT forensics (including assessment of security incidents and secure configuration of systems)	4
Microsoft solutions (including working with Microsoft Sentinel)	3
Systemic thinking and interface awareness	2

The answers to this question can be grouped into the following categories.

Communication and collaboration skills: The ability to communicate and collaborate effectively with others to achieve common goals.

Project management: The ability to effectively plan, organize and manage projects to achieve goals within a defined framework.

Awareness of IT security and data protection: understanding and compliance with measures to ensure IT security and data protection.

Flexibility: The ability to adapt quickly to changes and react flexibly to new requirements.

Willingness to learn: The willingness to continuously learn and develop in order to be able to use the latest methods and technologies.

Adaptability to flexible working methods and forms of organization: The ability to adapt quickly to new challenges and respond flexibly to change.

Openness to everything new: The willingness to accept and explore new ideas, technologies and approaches.

Digital competence: The ability to use and master digital tools and technologies.

Data analysis skills: The ability to analyze large amounts of data and draw insights from it to make informed decisions.

Communication skills in processes: The ability to communicate information effectively in processes and ensure that all parties involved are informed of the current status.

Awareness of project success: Awareness of the importance of project success and the ability to orchestrate on-premises and cloud services.

IT forensics: The understanding and mastery of IT forensics, including the assessment of security incidents and the secure configuration of systems.

Microsoft solutions: An understanding and mastery of Microsoft-based solutions, including how to use Microsoft Sentinel.

Systemic thinking and interface awareness: The ability to analyze and understand complex systems and the ability to link different aspects together.

Particularly noteworthy individual mentions were:

"Artificial intelligence as a colleague": This answer emphasizes the importance of developing skills in dealing with artificial intelligence in order to regard it as a "colleague" at work.

"Self Repair": This answer indicates the ability to recognize and fix problems independently, which could be an important self-management skill.

"Cybersecurity in all areas (e.g., secure coding)": The emphasis on "secure coding" shows how important it is to integrate security-related practices into software development.

Which employee skills are becoming less important?

43 universities responded to this question. The distribution is shown in the following table.

Category	Quantity
System administration	9
Specialization	8
IT expertise	6
Software programming	6
Hardware	5

The answers to these questions can be divided into the following categories for 2024.

System administration: This includes the mentions "System administration", "Classic system administration (on-premises)" and "Continue to operate legacy applications"

Specialization: This includes the mentions "specialization in a topic", "expertise" and "in-depth expert knowledge".

IT expertise: This category contains the mentions "IT expertise", "Purely technical topics" and "Operation of classic servers on-premises".

Hardware: This includes the mentions "hardware", "work on physical hardware" and "hardware knowledge".

Software programming: This category includes the entries "Programming", "Software programming" and "Building your own PC and servers".

Questions about the participating institutions and persons

The following diagrams provide an overview of the type and size of the facilities and the roles of the people involved.

The participating universities are distributed among the countries as follows.

Distribution of Participants Country - n=180

The following chart is based on the type of university.

The participating universities are distributed according to size as follows.

Distribution of Participants Size of University - n=176

The following table shows the roles of the participating person at their university

Role	Number of mentions
Head of an IT facility (computer center)	69
Other	50
CIO	21
Head of another central institution	11

Survey questionnaire

What type of university or research institution do you come from?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- University
- University of Applied Sciences
- Art / Music College
- Teacher training college
- Church university
- Cooperative State University
- State-recognized private university
- Research institution
- Miscellaneous

What is your role in the organization?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- CIO
- Head of an IT facility (computer center)
- Head of another central institution
- Miscellaneous

In which country is your facility located?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Germany
- Austria
- Switzerland

How many students does your university have?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Up to 5,000
- 5,001 to 15,000
- 15,001 to 30,000
- More than 30,000

Governance model

Which organizational model for IT governance is used at your university or research institution?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- CIO with staff function in the presidential staff
- Head of a central IT facility as CIO
- CIO committee
- CIO model is not established
- Chancellor or Vice President / as CIO
- Miscellaneous

Does your institution have a Chief Digital Officer (CDO) position?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No

Does your institution have an information security officer, IT-SiBe or CISO position?

- Yes
- No

Changes compared to the previous year

This section lists the top answers from the last year. Please indicate how you think the relevance of the topics has changed.

Please indicate whether, in your opinion, the relevance of the topic has increased, decreased or not changed since last year.

Please select the appropriate answer for each item:

Increase, Unchanged, Decrease

Questions on the key topic of "Digital sovereignty"

In your opinion, what are the most important dimensions or areas of responsibility that make up the "digital sovereignty" of your university?

What role do open source technologies play in your efforts to achieve digital sovereignty?

What role do cloud services and infrastructures outside your organization play in implementing your digital sovereignty strategy, and how do you secure them?

What partnerships and collaborations does your institution maintain with other universities or research institutions to strengthen digital sovereignty?

What measures has your organization taken to ensure the security and integrity of its IT infrastructure?

According to which standard is the information security management system ISMS developed at your institution?

- ISO 27
- BSI - IT baseline protection

- BSI - ZKI IT-Grundschutz profile for universities
- Own approach
- Other standard

Have you integrated a service provider for incident response?

- Yes
- No

How do you assess the risk of cyberattacks on your facility?

- From 1 - very low to 10 - very high

Core survey

The core survey consists of 12 questions.

What top trends do you see in the IT sector in general?

Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?

Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant for you in the coming year?

What topics are you currently working on strategically?

What new management tasks are you currently working on?

In which area are external services becoming more important for you?

In which areas are you investing more than before?

Which technologies are becoming more important for you?

What new services or technologies are you currently introducing?

What IT skills would you like to develop in your organization over the next year?

Which employee skills are becoming more important?

Which employee skills are becoming less important?

Surveys from previous years

2023

Survey: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7599852>

English version of the evaluation: <https://easychair.org/publications/download/9wWw>

2022

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6012935>

English version of the evaluation: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599926>

2021

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4530714>

Data appendix: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4530743>

English version of the results analysis: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4775115>

2020

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666168>

Data appendix: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666170>

2019

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590659>

Data appendix: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590683>

2018

Survey: <https://zenodo.org/record/1196427>

Data appendix: <https://zenodo.org/record/1183499>

The following tools were used to analyze the survey: Python with Pandas, Matplotlib and Seaborn, Scikit-learn, Difflib, Gradio, Docx Library, a local Sauerkraut 70B LLM